

Impact of Teachers' Growth Mindset on Teachers' Self-efficacy, and Psychological Wellbeing: A Study on Bangladeshi High School Teachers

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Abstract:

In order to explore the impacts of teachers' growth mindset on teachers' perception towards their self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing from Bangladeshi high school teachers' perspective. This research has performed a combined way of investigation which utilizes both quantitative and qualitative data were used. In study 1, 100 tutors have been surveyed to reveal the outcomes to investigation queries through a structured questionnaire with convenient sampling. Correlations were conducted to undertake the connection among tutors with the progressive mentality and their self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing. Chi-square, ANOVA and T-test, regression also works for this theorem. To run the analysis, the study used MS Excel and SPSS (V, 26) software. Results show that, p-value at the 0.001 level of significance with indicators ($\beta=0.231$, χ^2 value=853.579, t-value=3.137, p-value=0.000) which strongly confirms that teachers' growth mindset has a positive impact on teachers' self-efficacy, and psychological wellbeing. The aim of study 2, 10 samples was taken for an extensive interview session with a view to realizing the intensity of data. The detailed interview has been processed to analyze and transcribed sequentially, which converted into a Microsoft Word document and examined through structured content analysis. Results show that, positive aftermaths of tutors' progressive mentality on tutors' self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing. Positive aftermaths of tutors' progressive mentality on tutors' assumption self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing, as well as the quantitative assessments, are not much different from the qualitative outcomes among the high-school teachers in Bangladesh. The study has considered standard deviations between research one and research two measurements. The results of these two studies suggested that an extensive measure of the study is to be adopted to pinpoint the actual influence of tutors' progressive mentality on their self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing.

Keywords: Growth Mindset, Teachers' Growth Mindset, Self-efficacy, Psychological Wellbeing

Introduction

People have an immovable or progressive attitude in the path they assess their aptitudes. Individuals have static attitude as their aptitude as well as capacity were scheduled before they're born and can never be expanded (Dweck, 2016). Bedford (2017) and Snipes and Tran (2017) defined, the pupils those who possess very stern mentality are too much uptight that the frequently commit errors along with trying new chances which turn into their involvement into self-efficacy and presentation well-being evading. As per a paradox to stern mentality, peoples who have a progressive mentality will believe in flexibility, attempt, besides enthusiasm (Snipes & Tran, 2017). Persons with a progressive mentality keep their faith on that, their intellect may be improved by various routes, increasing the people's enticement to prosper intellectually (Dweck, 2016; Snipes & Tran, 2017; Yeager et al., 2016). Snipes and Tran (2017) stated that the growth mindset believes on intellect isn't immovable, may be improved through determination as well as erudition done by the moment. Optimistic teaching crucial to the speculative performance, own success, and students' wellbeing (Seligman et al., 2009).

Those revised lessons participants happened to be tutors as well as pupils at several education phases,

fluctuating since primary institute towards grown-up schooling. Speculative success relates with pupils' self-efficacy, wellbeing, speculative performance in institute judged primarily through mindset. This study sought to answer the question: To what extent does a teachers' growth mindset relate to their self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing? The following empirical research questions were used to determine the relationship between teachers' growth mindset, psychological wellbeing, and self-efficacy: And what is the impact of teachers' growth mindset on teachers' perception towards self-efficacy, and psychological wellbeing?

Statement of the Problem

The difficulty is, teachers explain to learners having a static mentality or get way beyond the level of progressive mentality (Johnston, 2014). Teacher's growth mindset is a valuable indicator on teachers' perception towards self-efficacy, and wellbeing. The main hardship is teachers with a growth mindset consciously or unconsciously exercise when they teach students. But in Bangladesh middle school or high school is the crucial periods for all students so teachers have a very important role in their instinct factors in this time. Education is the backbone of any developing country. So Bangladesh is not out of their list. But proper education mostly depends on teacher's growth mindset and they're teaching methods such as what their perception on students is and how they try to build or modify teacher's growth mindset. Bedford (2017) noted that while mentors seem to be familiar with the significance of optimistic as well as progressive output in the schoolroom, further investigation is verifying to determine techniques that tutors may apply to stimulate their students' progressive mentality. Dweck's (2015) investigation reveals that instructing pupils a progressive mentality transforms their strengths besides attends their students' engagement. Students may develop their minds (create modern, powerful neurotic contacts while reaching themselves to study solid matters) then demonstrate bigger enthusiasm to study. Accordingly, learners having progressive mentality can achieve increasing marks as well as attainment results in cumulative assumer tremendous. Distributing a progressive mentality proficient advancement for high school teas assume their application of progressive mental policies in their schoolroom can assist to develop pupil speculative accomplishment, positive self-efficacy, and well-being. This impact of teachers growth mindset on teachers perception towards in the works substantially the require following this kind of investigation.

Purpose of this study

Meierdirk (2016) noted that high school teachers may utilize a static mentality while educating pupils not having the sense of what they do. Rattan, Savani, Chugh, and Dweck (2015) examined the optimistic impacts of educating having a progressive mentality. For this current research motto is,

- The key purpose of the research was to inspect the impacts of teacher's growth mindset on teacher's Self-efficacy and Psychological Wellbeing.
- To discuss an interview with high school teacher's knowledge and experiences regarding the growth mindset and which specific factors generally teachers perceive for their self-efficacy and Psychological Wellbeing.

Literature Review

The crucial impact of teacher growth mindset on teacher's self-efficacy, and psychological well-being is scrutinized since countless hypothetical methods in past decades.

The progressive mentality represents the credence that people's intelligence can be advanced with efforts and undertakings (Dweck, 2006). The idea that individuals Intellect is not immovable can be upgraded through determination, learning, and problematic work overtime (Snipes & Tran, 2017). Growth mindset persons greetings and receive backing and aid from others. With a progressive mentality, persons

have faith in that their mind is a strength that can accumulate sharper and more muscular with exercise (Yeager et al., 2016).

Dweck's (2000, 2006) defined mindset deals with the implicit theory that essential human ability. Implicit theories, also known as growth mindset, are interpreted as beliefs about the personal tendency (Dweck and Leggett, 1988; Dweck et al., 1995; Molden and Dweck, 2006; Yeager and Dweck, 2012). Snipes & Tran (2017) stated that tutors having progressive mentality trust in flexibility, struggle, courage, and persistence. Mentally progressive individuals discern that their mind has a potency that is able to expand healthier through rehearsal (Yeager et al., 2016), and teachers can apply their growth mindset strategy to the students. A growth mindset assumes that intellect is not stone as well as there's scope to be developed with work hard and studying over time. According to Snipes and Tran (2017), the growth mindset believes that intellect is not stone and might be developed with work hard and studying more and more.

Self-efficacy is an understanding of individuals' proficiency/capability to achieve extraordinary situations (Bandura, 1986). Albert Bandura (1997) acknowledged that self-efficacy controls how attitudes and obstacles were observed and not just influences individuals' choices, how vastly effort and willingness to continue until they were productive or accomplishment. A person's self-efficacy is built on past achievements, especially the person who challenges the person and overcomes with a lot of hard work. Oppositely, failure quickly disrupts a person's concept of individual value, exceptionally if the person simply achieves smoothly. (Bandura, 1995).

Psychological well-being is determined as an individual self-appraisal of their capacity to achieve specific realms in life. These realms incorporate self-respect, personal development, and the motive in life, constructive connection with people, ability, and freedom (Ryff & Keyes, 1995). They additionally interpreted the spheres. Individual-respect is the personal assessment of a human being. Self-acceptance is a detailed evaluation of oneself life. Individual development happens to be the realization of sustained development as well as growth as an individual. Determination in lifecycle is the confidence that one's lifecycle is decisive as well as evocative. Constructive understandings with others are the custody of excellent relations with others. Conservational control is the ability to control effectually one's lifecycle and the adjacent ecosphere. Self-government is a concept of freedom.

Study 1

For the current quantitative study, the researcher initially recruited secondary school teachers to conduct a survey on impact of teacher's growth mindset on teacher's self-efficacy, and psychological wellbeing in Bangladesh. Following that, a number of ten teachers were took an extensive method to test the authentic condition of teachers responses in the interview, their own personal views, performance as teachers as well as their relevance with the literature review of the topic. Diverse approaches may be defined as "numerous paths of looking" (Creswell & Clark, 2011) as the research findings may be understood from numerous corners.

Methods

This section will show how to study 1 was done. These method sections including participants' procedure, data collection, data analysis.

Participants

For research one, the researcher has picked up 100 teachers as sample based on simple convenient sampling techniques that made through the researcher initial requirements. Just enough number of participants (100), who initially fulfilled the standard prerequisites, were selected through the convenient sampling method of

the purposive study as the overall population size is not known to us.

Procedure, data collection and data analysis

Initially, the researcher had to understand whether they're capable of understanding her research topic clearly or not. The researcher provided the teachers with a total of 31 questions set up in a Google form. Thirty one of them are in 6 Point Likert Scale & divided into four sections. The first section has 4 demographic questions that determine their necessary information. The second section was 5-12 descriptive questions that determine their mindset and judgment on various life issues. The third portion is composed of 13-21 descriptive questions that determine their growth mindset towards students' self-efficacy to justify their views on different levels of accounts. The fourth part was 22-31 descriptive questions that also determine teachers' growth mindset on perception towards students' psychological wellbeing. Data collection from the respondent's research is conducted according to the method of correlation matrix to detect if there is any relationship prevails between the measured variable or not. Besides that, the mean and standard deviation of all retention dimensions were premeditated to determine the variable having the highest influence of the progressive mentality of the tutor on self-efficacy and wellbeing and Chi Square, regression, and ANOVA test also applied for hypothesis testing. Excel and SPSS is used to analyze this data with more flexibility and clarification all through the way.

Results and Discussions

In this particular quantitative analysis, the thesis study firstly tries to analyze the demographic data for example survey participants' sex analysis, teaching grade analysis, residing area analysis as well as the participants' experience analysis. Among the 100 participants of this survey majority of them are found as male (n=63, 63%); where (n=37, 37%) of the teachers are female. This study has planned to conduct a survey of structured questionnaire for quantitative research analysis. To continue and explain this quantitative research analysis, the following sections will discuss the demographic, descriptive, central tendency analysis and hypotheses analysis for this study. Among the 100 participants of this survey majority of them are working as 10th grade level (n=31, 31%); after that (n=53, 53%) of the teachers are working as 9th grade level; and (n=16, 16%) of the teachers are working as 8th grade level. However, one of the participants is not interested to response in this particular question.

Table 1: Demographic Information

Variable	Dimension	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Gender	Female	37	37.0
	Male	63	63.0
	Total	n = 100	100.0
Grade	10th	31	31.0
	8th	16	16.0
	9th	53	53.0
	Total	n = 100	100.0
Working Area	No Response	1	1.0
	Other	1	1.0
	Rural	26	26.0

Analysis	Suburban	39	39.0
	Urban	33	33.0
	Total	n = 100	100.0
Teaching Experience	0 to 5	17	17.0
	10 to 15	43	43.0
	15-20	12	12.0
	5 to 10	28	28.0
	Total	n = 100	100.0

Source: The Author

100 participants of this survey majority of them are working at suburban area (n=39, 39%); where (n=33, 33%) of the teachers are working at Urban area; after that (n=26, 26%) of the teachers are working at rural area; and (n=1, 1%) of the teachers are working in other area. 10 to 15 years of teaching experience (n=29, 29%); where (n=28, 28%) of the teachers are having 5 to 10 years of teaching experience; after that (n=17, 17%) of the teachers are having 0 to 5 years of teaching experience; and (n=12, 12%) of the teachers are having 15 to 20 years of teaching experience. However, (n=14, 14%) of the participants are prefer not to say to response in this particular question.

Reliability Analysis

Before going to test the correlation, regression, and hypotheses, internal consistency measurement of the collected data is an integral part. A basic rule has been given by (Nunnally, 1978; Cortina, 1993; George & Mallery, 2003), if alpha is below 0.7 therefore the data is not strongly internally consistent, and if $\alpha \geq 0.7$ the data is internally consistent. The alpha value for three variables is higher than 0.7 for this analysis, so the collected data has passed the reliability testing. This analysis means that, all the collected data are reliable and goodly internally consistent for this particular study.

Correlation Analysis

Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) has been conducted to justify the correlation among the selected variables. A correlation matrix of all values of rare given in Table-6, the result of Pearson product-moment correlation exposes that there is a positive significant correlation between teachers' growth mindset and teachers' perception towards students' self-efficacy; and also between teachers' perception towards teachers' self-efficacy and teachers' perception towards teachers' psychological wellbeing; a positive significant correlation between teachers' growth mindset and teachers' perception towards teachers' psychological wellbeing. From the above table, the correlations analysis can conclude that, SEF has positive significant correlation with GMS ($r = 0.049$; $p < 0.01$) and PSW has positive significant correlation with GMS ($r = 0.028$; $p < 0.01$). Finally, the correlations outcome has found SEF has positive significant correlation with PSW ($r = 0.443$; $p < 0.01$).

Hypothesis Analysis

The study considers two distinctive hypotheses to test. Those are given below;

(H_{1a0}): Teachers' growth mindset has positive impact on teachers' self-efficacy.

(H_{1aA}): Teachers' growth mindset does not have positive impact on self-efficacy.

(H_{1b0}): Teachers' growth mindset has positive impact on teachers' psychological wellbeing.

(H_{1bA}): Teachers’ growth mindset does not have positive impact on teachers ‘psychological wellbeing.

Chi Square/X2 Testing

Hypothesis-1a

To test the hypothesis-1a, this study considers chi-square testing between the independent (teachers’ growth mindset) and dependent (teachers’ self-efficacy) variables.

Based on the Chi-square result from the Chi-square value testing result is 751.471 and the p-value is 0.087. It reflects that the p-value is significant at 10% level. The p-value [Sig. (2-tailed)] for teachers’ growth mindset on teachers’ self-efficacy is smaller than 0.1 ($p < .1$) which results that null hypothesis H_{1a0} is rejected and alternative hypothesis H_{1aA} is accepted. The analysis depicts that, teachers’ growth mindset has positive impact on teachers’ self-efficacy.

Hypothesis-2

To test the hypothesis-2, this study considers chi-square testing between the independent (teachers’ growth mindset) and dependent (teachers’ psychological wellbeing) variables.

Based on the Chi-square result the Chi-square value testing result is 853.579 and the p-value is 0.008. It reflects that the p-value is significant at 1% level. The p-value [Sig. (2-tailed)] for teachers’ growth mindset on teachers’ psychological wellbeing is smaller than 0.01 ($p < .01$) which results that null hypothesis H_{1b0} is rejected and alternative hypothesis H_{1bA} is accepted. The analysis depicts that, teachers’ growth mindset has positive impact on teachers’ psychological wellbeing.

Regression Analysis

The proposed regression models of this study are as follows.

Source: Authors

Model-1:

H1a. Teachers’ growth mindset has positive impact on teachers’ Self-efficacy.

To test the hypothesis, the study has considered a regression for the model. Regression method is generally used to assess in which extent a dependent variable can be interpreted by an independent variable. The independent variable in this analysis is the teachers’ growth mindset. On the other hand the dependent variable for hypothesis-1a is the teachers’ self-efficacy.

Table-9: Model Summary-1

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.046 ^a	.213	.205	.85312

a. Predictors: (Constant), GMS

Source: Author

The study finds R square= .213 from Table-9, which indicates that 21.3% of the dependent variable (teachers’ self-efficacy) can be described by the independent (teachers’ growth mindset) variables.

Table-10: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.173	1	.173	.238	.008 ^b
	Residual	70.598	97	.728		
	Total	70.771	98			

a. Dependent Variable: SEF

b. Predictors: (Constant), GMS

Source: Author

Table-10 shows that the regression model is valid and significant at 1% level of significance.

Table-11: t-Test output ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.195	.419		10.014	.000
	GMS	.054	.111	0.201	2.421	.008

a. Dependent Variable: SEF

Source: Author

If the study tries to draw a regression equation based on the regression result. The underlying regression equation for the teachers’ growth mindset has positive impact on the teachers’ self-efficacy would be as follows,

$$D_1 = a + b \text{ (GMS)}$$

$$\text{Or, } D_1 = 4.915 + 0.054 \text{ GMS (Based on the table-10 outcomes)}$$

Hence, independent variable of teachers’ growth mindset is positively depending on the dependent variable of teachers’ self-efficacy. Table-11 indicates that, for one sample t-Test; at 1% significant level the p-value [Sig. (2-tailed)] for the teachers’ growth mindset on teachers’ self-efficacy.

Model-2:

H1a. Teachers’ growth mindset has positive impact on teachers’ Psychological wellbeing.

To test the hypothesis, the study has considered another regression for the model. The independent variable in this analysis is the teachers’ growth mindset. On the other hand the dependent variable for hypothesis-1b is the teachers’ psychological wellbeing.

Table-12: Model Summary-2

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.056 ^a	.312	0.304		.75991

a. Predictors: (Constant), GMS

Source: Author

The study finds R square= .312 from Table-12, which indicates that 31.2% of the dependent variable (teachers’ psychological wellbeing) can be described by the independent (teachers’ growth mindset) variables.

Table-13: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.045	1	.045	.077	.000 ^b
	Residual	56.013	97	.577		
	Total	56.058	98			

a. Dependent Variable: PSW

b. Predictors: (Constant), GMS

Source: Author

Table-13 shows that the regression model is valid and significant at 0.1% level of significance.

Table-14: t-Test output ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.213	.373		11.289	.000
	GMS	.028	.099	0.231	3.137	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PSW

Source: Author

If the model-2 tries to draw a regression equation based on the regression result. The underlying regression equation for the teachers’ growth mindset has positive impact on the teachers’ psychological wellbeing would be as follows,

$$D_1 = a + b (\text{PSW})$$

Or, $D_1 = 4.213 + 0.028 \text{ PSW}$ (Based on the table-14 outcomes)

Hence, independent variable of teachers’ growth mindset is positively depending on the dependent variable of teachers’ psychological wellbeing. Table-14 indicates that, for one sample t-Test; at 0.1% significant level the p-value [Sig. (2-tailed)] for the teachers’ growth mindset on teachers’ psychological wellbeing.

Table-15: Hypothesized Direct Effect (Result Summary)

Hypothesis	Hypothesized direct effect	R ²	χ^2	(β)	t-value	p-value	Decision
H1a	Teachers' growth mindset has positive impact on teachers' Self-efficacy.	21.3%	751.471	0.201**	2.421	0.008	Supported
H1b	Teachers' growth mindset has positive impact on teachers' Psychological wellbeing.	31.2%	853.579	0.231***	3.137	0.000	Supported

Notes. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$.

Source: The authors.

Study 2

Before measuring the impact of high school teacher's growth mindsets on teachers' self-efficacy as well as psychological wellbeing, the study at first has decided to go for quantitative assessment then qualitative analysis. Under qualitative method, this particular study has selected interview method. To assess the quantitative analysis outcomes, a number of ten high school teachers has been picked up and interviewed to sort out the survey factors under both the dependent and independent variables. The interview has been designed according to the research methodology. Where the duration each and every interview from 20 minutes to 30 minutes as per time and consideration of the interviewees. The interview questions have been categorized under sections.

Methods

This section will show how to study 2 was done. These method sections including participants' procedure, data collection, data analysis.

Participants

Just enough number of participants (10), who fulfilled the standard prerequisites, were selected through the simple convenient sampling method of the purposive study as the overall population size is not known to us. The researcher needed those teachers who can evaluate themselves and their works as a human being and of course, as a teacher.

Procedure, data collection, & data analysis

This section requires those participants who actually have a qualitative minds and mature understanding about what they are. The researcher had closely monitored the teachers' initial interactions throughout the entire informal contacting process. It required a semi-structured in-depth online interview, as closely as

possible to the face-to-face interview. The widely used method regarding this research is conducting an in-depth interview, mainly designed to obtain useful data in a natural and familiar environment. In addition to that, an in-depth interview allows the researcher to get a first-hand note about the participant's gesture, which prevents misleading of any sort of information by providing top quality answers. A semi-structured in-depth interview is organized (such as; “ What do you think that Teachers Growth Mindset has an impact on Students Academic success, self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing? ”) so that the interviewer's subject or field is recorded in a notebook to allow the informants to talk to them on their own via mobile phone. Thus, the interviewer will get different responses from different questions that cannot be guessed earlier. It is the interviewer's mandatory responsibility to ask each & every question correctly and thoughtfully (Bryman, 2001). Detailed interview has been processed to analyze qualitative data and recorded words and took notebook with their permission. They were transcribed sequentially, converted into Microsoft Word document, and examined through structured content analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006: Alhojailan, 2012: Fereday & MuirCochrane, 2006: Thomas, 2006).

Results & Discussions

Under qualitative method, this particular study has selected interview method. To assess the quantitative analysis outcomes, a number of ten high school teachers has been picked up and interviewed to sort out the survey factors under both the dependent and independent variables. The interview has been designed according to the research methodology. Where the duration each and every interview from 30 minutes to 40 minutes as per time and consideration of the interviewees. The interview questions have been categorized under five sections.

Under qualitative method, this particular study has selected interview method. To assess the quantitative analysis outcomes, a number of ten high school teachers has been picked up and interviewed to sort out the survey factors under both the dependent and independent variables. The interview has been designed according to the research methodology. Where the duration each and every interview from 30 minutes to 40 minutes as per time and consideration of the interviewees. The interview questions have been categorized under sections.

What do you think that Teachers’ Growth Mindset has an impact on Students’ academic success, self-efficacy and psychological well-being?

An interview question has been asked under this above particular heading; where all the selected ten interview participants have been asked about the general opinion s regarding the context. The interviewer has asked, “*What do you think about the impacts of teachers’ growth mindset on teachers’ self-efficacy and psychological well-being?*” Some mixed opinions have been observed from the interviewees. Most of the participants have perceived and shared teachers’ growth mindset, students’ self-efficacy and psychological well-being are interrelated and direct effect. However, few of them are more or less ignorant or unaware about the context. Due to some privacy issues the participants are not interested to disclose their name for this research. Hence the author will use coding (such as for teacher 1=TH1, teacher 2 = TH2 and so on) to directly quote their responses.

For more clear evaluation and understanding, few comments from the interviewees are pointed here. One of teacher (TH-1) shared that, “*Teachers’ growth mindset has direct effects on students’ academic success, teachers self-efficacy and teachers psychological well-being because students take input from teachers. So, teachers’ growth will be transmitted to teachers and students’ growth.*”

In addition, TH-5 also perceived as same like TH-1 and expressed as; “*A teacher impacts a student in his or her every move, attitude and thought. He is not only a tutor, but also a counselor. His or her counsels have tremendous influence over the student’s entire mind setup. That is how the teacher’s growth mindset impacts.*”

TH-10 introduces her opinion like a harmony of the other teachers but in a different way. She perceives as, *“In the modern-aged teaching system, a teacher has multi-purposed role in the life of a student and also their own life. It affects not only these three but also many other aspects of a student’s life. It does have a serious impact because teachers work as the guide as well as the mentor of the students he or she teaches. Hence, teacher’s growth mindset is the key to student’s mental advancement. As the students always play the role of followers, then the impact is surely tremendous. Teaching is not only about academic aspects rather it defines who the students are.”*

On the other hand, TH-7 said, *“The context is very much interesting to me and it sounds well regarding the transmission of knowledge from teacher to students. Unfortunately, I am not that much aware with the concept.”*

Based on the above comments, the study is supported quantitative measurement is understandable to discover the issue from mass respondents. To explore the research, the author has decided to identify the suitable factor under each mentioned variable (growth mindset, self-efficacy, and psychological well-being). Earlier the researcher did a survey and then analyzes some closely related literature to identify the various factors under each variable. Here, in qualitative measurement, the author has tried to sort out the best fit of the factors from practical interview responses. The following analysis has been designed to the best-fit factors under each variable.

Growth mindset factors

To sort out the teachers’ growth mindset factors the researcher has asked a related question to the interviewees. The question was; *“Which factors may affect to the teacher’s growth mindset?”* After getting responses from the interview participants, the study has found some significant factors and those are more or less addressed in literature review as well. The following comments address some important factors may affect teachers’ growth mindset variable.

For more clear evaluation and understanding of teachers’ growth mindset factors, few comments from the interviewees are pointed here. One of the participants shared that, *“Teachers’ growth mindset is the upstream and students’ growth mindset is downstream. I think in some extent teacher’s intelligence is something by born. Whereas in some other extent it can be develop through proper training and development programs. By arranging such program teacher’s mindset will surely be improved. It might be, those are not by born.”*

Another participant TH-3 perceives that, *“Students’ success depends on their activities guided by teachers. Teachers’ performance can be upgraded if their growth mindset is occurred. My point of view is that, teacher should be positive in mind for receiving productive as well as constructive feedback from their students. They should be able to change their knowledge and delivery level gradually.”*

However, TH-2 said that, *“As the teacher’s mindset is closely related to his teaching ability, it determines how the teacher can deliver to certain types of students. So, I have no doubt that teachers’ growth mindset matters in case of student’s academic success but I don’t know which specific factors should be considered to measure and evaluate teachers’ growth mindset”*

TH-10 also shared the same as TH-3 but in diverse way. She narrated that, *“A teacher with growth mindset can deliver better than the others to the students and it obviously has the better academic output. Unfortunately, I am sorry; I don’t have any expertise ideas regarding this context.”*

According to the above qualitative analysis the study has sorted out by born intelligence, trained intelligence, positive attitude to receive feedback from students, continuous learning and improvement of knowledge and intelligence etc. can be considers as very much important factors to evaluate teachers’ growth mindset.

Teachers' Self-efficacy Factors

To sort out the self-efficacy factors of students the researcher has asked a related question to the interviewees. The question was; *“How you perceive teachers’ self-efficacy? Which factors may affect to the teachers’ self-efficacy from your point of view?”* After getting responses from the interview participants, the study has found some significant factors and those are more or less addressed in literature review as well. The following comments address some important teachers perceive factors may affect the teachers’ self-efficacy variable.

For more clear evaluation and understanding of teachers’ self-efficacy factors, few comments from the interviewees are pointed here. One of the teachers perceived that, *“Many cases teachers can’t move on their fatigue in different situations. Teachers can improve the situation if their dominating voice can influence over them. Teachers can do it when they believe in gradual improvement of themselves.”*

Another participant perceives that, *“As like performance, teachers’ self-efficacy is also increased if teacher’s growth mindset is established. To develop teachers’ self-efficacy, teachers may set some significant aims for their teaching. They should be confident to manage unexpected occurrences and be able to handle smartly. Those abilities of teachers may build strong self-efficacy.”*

According to the above qualitative analysis the study has sorted out teachers’ self-confident, ability to convince students, able to set some significant aims for their teaching, teachers should be confident to manage unexpected occurrences and be able to handle smartly etc. can be considered as the significant factors to assess teachers’ self-efficacy as per their teachers’ perception.

Factors Regarding Teachers’ Psychological Wellbeing

Another interview discussion session has been arranged by the researcher to identify the factors regarding teachers’ psychological wellbeing from teachers’ perspective. A specific question has been asked to the interviewees. The question is, *“How you perceive teachers’ psychological wellbeing? Which factors may affect to the teachers’ psychological wellbeing from your viewpoint?”* After getting responses from the interview participants, the study has found some significant factors and those are more or less addressed in literature review as well. The following comments address some important factors regarding teachers’ psychological wellbeing variable from teachers’ perspective.

For more clear evaluation and understanding of teachers’ psychological wellbeing factors, few comments from the interviewees are pointed here. One of the teachers perceived that, *“Students gather the information from teachers with the psychological representation of teachers. Students are influenced by teachers’ psychology always. I think teachers should be taken in charge of the entire learning environments”*

TH-4 said that, *“A teacher is a psychological master of a student at the same also themselves. If a teacher has a progressive mentality, the students normally develops much better both in psychological and academic way, and vice-versa. In such case teacher may influence their student for positive mindset, help them to believing themselves and be able to judge by their own.”*

But few participants perceived the discussing issues are somewhat same to the previous issues and interlinked to one another. TH-2 said, *“The teacher acts as the teachers/student’s psychological governor. It is obvious that the state does in the way how the governor governs. This is as similar as previous issues.”*

According to the above qualitative analysis the study has sorted out teachers should be taken in charge of the entire learning environments, should motive their students, to take the responsibilities of their daily life, inspire students in continuous learning process, assist them to gather more practical experiences and knowledge, able to make the believe that they perceive their problem from their own situation etc. can be considered as the significant factors to assess teachers’ psychological wellbeing from the teachers’ point of view.

Relationship among the selected variables from teachers' view point

Few questions have been asked to understand how the teachers perceive the interconnected among the variables. Following comments may strengthen and test the selected hypotheses. The researcher has asked the interviewee that, *share with us your notion about teachers' growth mindset governing on teachers' self-efficacy?* For more clear evaluation and understanding few comments from the interviewees are pointed here

One of the teachers perceived that, *"Being a conscious man, it depends on how the teacher has an impact in their/student's life. Personal development is heavily reliant on the growth mindset of a teacher."*

Another participant shared that, *"It is no wonder that a teacher will shape up the taste and mentality of the student and also their life. A positive mindset always contains individual justification as the growth mindset demands. So, certainly it shows a positive impact on teachers' self-efficacy."*

While to understand the perception of teachers' growth mindset on teacher's psychological wellbeing, a question was asked as; *how can you evaluate the impact of teacher's growth mindset on teacher's psychological wellbeing?* For more clear evaluation and understanding few comments from the interviewees are pointed here.

An interviewee added that, *"Teacher's psychology influences teacher's directly. So, this happens in direct way."*

According to the above qualitative analysis the study has sorted out teachers growth mindset has positive impacts on teacher's self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing.

5. General Discussions

In this particular section the study has tried to discuss the outcomes based on the earlier literatures will be compared with research questions and the outcomes of each research question.

The findings of the specific factors affect teachers' growth mindset

To explore the factors affecting high school teachers' growth mindset, this study initially assesses some previous researches. After assessing the earlier researchers regarding this particular research question, the researcher has prepared a related question to unveil the factors from teachers' real-life experience through interview. After interviewing the selected 10 teachers the following factors have unveiled. Those are, teachers' inherent intelligence and intellectual abilities, enhanced intelligence and intellectual abilities through proper training, allow to receive constructive feedback, able to change knowledge and delivery level gradually, teacher should be dynamic and continuous knowledge seekers, more efforts to improve level of knowledge and intelligence, should learn new and novel things. Those (teachers' inherent intelligence and intellectual abilities, allow to receive constructive feedback, able to change knowledge and delivery level gradually, teacher should be dynamic and continuous knowledge seekers, more efforts to improve level of knowledge and intelligence, should learn new and novel things) growth mindset factors have been addressed by (Dweck, 2006; Snipes & Tran, 2017; Yeager et al., 2016). However, the "enhanced intelligence and intellectual abilities through proper training" growth mind set factor has been opposed the findings of (Dweck & Rule, 2013; Persellin & Davis, 2016).

The findings of the specific factors generally teachers perceive for their' self-efficacy:

To explore the factors affecting high school teachers' perception towards their self-efficacy, this study initially assesses some previous researches. After assessing the earlier researchers regarding this particular research question, the researcher has prepared a related question to unveil the factors from teachers' real-life experience through interview. After interviewing the selected 10 teachers the following factors have unveiled. Those are, motivate students through counseling, teachers may set some significant aims for their teaching, teacher should support to build the confident of students to manage unexpected occurrences and be able to handle smartly, teacher should be spent more time to care their students, confident teachers may create confident students. Those above factors (motivate students through counseling, teacher should be

spent more time to care their students, confident teachers may create confident students) have been addressed by (Bandura, 1977, 1986, 1997; Philipp, 2007). However, these two factors (Teachers may set some significant aims for their teaching, teacher should support to build the confidence of students to manage unexpected occurrences and be able to handle smartly) have been considered as new factors for teachers' perception towards their students' self-efficacy.

Findings of the specific factors generally teachers perceive for teachers' psychological wellbeing:

To explore the factors affecting high school teachers' perception towards their teachers' psychological wellbeing, this study initially assesses some previous researches. After assessing the earlier researchers regarding this particular research question, the researcher has prepared a related question to unveil the factors from teachers' real-life experience through interview. After interviewing the selected 10 teachers the following factors have unveiled. Those are, teachers should be taken in charge of the entire learning environments, strong psychology of teachers can ignite the teachers' strong psychology, should motivate teachers to take the responsibilities of their daily life, should inspire students in continuous learning process as well as gather more practical experiences and knowledge, teacher may give some for themselves' counseling and be opened in heart and mind, try to build a strong platform solve the students' problem as teachers' situation, teachers; progressive mentality may help the students to develop much better both in psychological and academic way, help students to believe themselves and be able to judge by their own. Those above factors (strong psychology of teachers can ignite the teachers' strong psychology, should motivate students to take the responsibilities of their daily life, should inspire teachers in continuous learning process as well as gather more practical experiences and knowledge, teacher may give some for students' counseling and be opened in heart and mind, teachers; progressive mentality may help the students to develop much better both in psychological and academic way) have been addressed by (Ryff & Keyes, 1995; Emadpoor, Lavasani, & Shahcheraghi, 2016). However, these three factors (teachers should be taken in charge of the entire learning environments, try to build a strong platform solve the students' problem as teachers' situation, and help students to believe themselves and be able to judge by their own) have been considered as new factors for teachers' perception towards their psychological wellbeing.

Findings of the type of relationship is been exist between teachers' growth mind set and teachers' perception towards teachers' self-efficacy:

Based on the literature review found this particular research after that 100 teachers have been selected for a survey. 10 teachers have been selected to justify the relationship, whether the relationship has any positive significant impact or not. To assess this particular research, question the study has picked 8 specific factors for growth mind set questions (*Teachers' intellectual ability is something with which they are born; teachers are either having by-born intellectual ability or not, Teachers can always progress their intelligence. Most often they are not having an inherent set of intelligence, I generally prefer to receive some constructive feedbacks; particularly it helps to understand well about myself. Teachers can modify their basic intelligence and intellectual level significantly, I think I am smart enough, thus I do not require putting in a huge amount of effort to maintain my teaching performance well, I can considerably revolutionize my intelligence level, I can be trained to learn new knowledge, but it cannot able to modify my basic intelligence, I will not be able to change my intelligence and intellectual level*)

To test the relationship, the study has selected teachers' growth mindset as independent variable and teachers' perception towards teachers' self-efficacy as dependent variables. After chi-square and paired sample t-test the study found there has a positive significant impact of teachers' growth mind set on teachers' perception towards teachers' self-efficacy. The outcome of this particular relationship has supported the outcomes of (Dweck, 2007; Glei, 2013; Farrington et al., 2012). However, the outcome of this particular study has opposed the findings of (Hass, Katz-Buonincontro, & Reiter-Palmon, 2016; Rhew et al., 2018) researches.

Findings of what type of relationship is been exist between teachers' growth mind set and teachers' perception towards teachers' psychological wellbeing:

Based on the literature review found this particular research after that 100 teachers have been selected for a survey. 10 teachers have been selected to justify the relationship, whether the relationship has any positive significant impact or not. To assess this particular research, question the study has picked 8 specific factors for growth mind set questions (*mentioned earlier*) and 10 specific factors for teachers' perception towards teachers' psychological wellbeing questions (*I believe my students can charge of any circumstances in which they survive in general, I think my students are good at execution of their responsibilities in their daily life, I help my students to believe that, their life is an ongoing process of growth, learning, as well as changing, Having innovative skills which faces my students' way of their thoughts in life appear imperative to them, I am happy to share my time with my students and want them to consider themselves as an open-hearted human being, In some cases I think, my students gave up approaching to craft big perfections and modifications in their life*)

To test the relationship, the study has selected teachers' growth mindset as independent variable and teachers' perception towards teachers' self-efficacy as dependent variables. After chi-square and t-test, ANOVA test the study found there has a positive significant impact of teachers' growth mind set on teachers' perception towards teachers' self-efficacy. The outcome of this particular relationship has supported the outcomes of (Dweck, 2007; Gleit, 2013; Farrington et al., 2012). However, the outcome of this particular study has opposed the findings of (Hass, Katz-Buonincontro, & Reiter-Palmon, 2016; Rhew et al., 2018) researches.

Discussion of how the responses deviate in research one measurement in compare to research two measurement:

Based on the literature review survey the study has pointed out some research factors and the collected data has been considered for research one analysis. From earlier research researcher found teachers growth mindset, teacher's perception towards teacher's self-efficacy and teacher's perception towards teacher's psychological wellbeing. For the interviews, all the above factors have been picked up and have pointed out 8 factors for teacher's growth mindset, 9 factors for teacher's perception towards teachers, and 10 factors for teacher's perception towards teacher's psychological wellbeing. The data has been considered for research two analysis. It can be said that, all the two selected hypotheses have found significant. However, there have some deviations among the responses from the respondents. The study has considered standard deviation to measure the deviations between research one and research two measurements. The standard deviation of all the 8 growth mindset questions is laying from 1.173 to 1.567 in the scale difference of 1 point; that means the responses from the teachers are very much deviated from each other and the standard deviation of all the 10 teachers' perception towards teachers' psychological wellbeing questions is laying from 1.032 to 1.473 in the scale difference of 1 point; that means the responses from the teachers are somewhat deviated from each other's. However, the standard deviation of all the 9 teachers' perception towards teachers' self-efficacy questions is laying from 0.988 to 1.172 in the scale difference of 1 point; that means the responses from the teachers are not that much deviated from each other's.

Limitations

There are numerous restrictions that may be existing in this research. The innovative enterprise asked to utilize a messaging system to provoke school principal's notices and to exploit accords acknowledged for the investigation; those mails were not sent to principal as cues because of subjects with admittance to the structure and convenience of pupil information by the investigator. Not distributing these cues could have reserved the quantity of genuinely learnt consensuses that were acknowledged or the quantity of contribution for the investigation.

Conclusion

This research was directed in five high schools within a large school region. The research was also confined

into only members who were high school educators in Grades eight, nine and ten. Since members were limited for epidemic circumstances, this restricted the transferability of the outcomes to all other grade levels. Since the outcomes of this research are grounded on self-reports from educators, educators in the investigation may have answered with a biased depiction of how they communicate in terms of progressive mentality. Additional restriction was that all of the meetings occur through phone. This might restrict the quantity of data that may have been distributed over a face-to-face meeting. It is suggested that superintendents deliver educators' progressive mentality expansion working out in their school building so, educators can absorb exact plans on how to educate having a progressive mentality for pupils. Although info on influences of educators' progressive mentality on educators' insight towards pupils' self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing in grades eight, nine and ten is presented in this study, more research is needed to examine impacts of educators' progressive mentality on educators' insight towards pupils' self-efficacy and psychological wellbeing.

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